

Evaluating the Balance between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation in Aspiring Teachers: A Case Study at a Public University

1st Author **Sheeza Asif**

Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan Pakistan

Email: sheezaasif35@gmail.com

2nd Author **Deng Xiaoqing**

Faculty of Education Southwest University,

Chongqing China

Email: ddddddd@email.swu.edu.cn

3rd Author **Shaharia Sharmin Shrabonty**

College of international study,

Southwest University, Chongqing, China

Email: Shahariasharmin1997@gmail.com

Corresponding Author Akash Mahamud

Faculty of Teacher Education

Southwest University, Chongqing China

Email: md.suvro@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study aims to examine the intricate balance between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation among prospective teachers enrolled in the Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) program at Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. Motivation, a critical determinant in the educational and professional trajectories of future educators, was analyzed to assess how internal and external factors influence teaching preparedness. Using a descriptive research design, a sample of 74 students was surveyed with a 36-item Likert scale that evenly distributed items between intrinsic (internal satisfaction, intellectual curiosity) and extrinsic (external rewards, social validation) motivators.

The results revealed a slight predominance of extrinsic motivation (mean score = 3.93) over intrinsic motivation (mean score = 3.89), suggesting that external factors such as grades, teacher validation, and task ease were marginally more influential than internal factors like personal challenge and problem-solving. Despite this, intrinsic motivation remained strong, particularly in areas related to intellectual engagement and independent problem-solving. A notable finding was the significant negative correlation between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, indicating that an increase in reliance on external motivators tends to diminish internal motivation, and vice versa.

These findings offer significant insights for teacher education programs, highlighting the need for a balanced motivational strategy that integrates both intrinsic and extrinsic elements. Future educators should be encouraged to cultivate a passion for teaching through personal satisfaction while also being guided by external milestones, such as academic performance and career prospects. The study recommends further exploration into how these motivational orientations evolve over time, and their impact on long-term teaching effectiveness and job satisfaction. By aligning curricula with both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators, educational institutions can better prepare future teachers for the multifaceted demands of the profession.

Introduction

In the realm of education, motivation stands as a pivotal determinant of both academic achievement and professional success. For educators, particularly those in training, the types and levels of motivation they possess can significantly influence their teaching practices, their interactions with students, and ultimately, the educational outcomes they help produce. Motivation is broadly categorized into two types: intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation refers to the drive that comes from within an individual, driven by personal satisfaction, curiosity, and the inherent pleasure of learning or mastering a subject. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is influenced by external factors, such as rewards, recognition, grades, or the expectations of others.

The importance of understanding motivation in prospective teachers cannot be overstated. These future educators will soon be responsible for shaping the minds and attitudes of young learners, and their own motivations will undoubtedly play a crucial role in how effectively they fulfill this role. Intrinsic motivation is often seen as the ideal form of motivation in education, as it is associated with deep engagement, a love for learning, and a commitment to excellence in teaching. Teachers who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to inspire their students, create dynamic learning environments, and remain passionate about their profession over the long term.

However, extrinsic motivation also holds significant value, particularly in structured educational settings where external benchmarks and outcomes, such as grades, certifications, and job placements, are emphasized. Extrinsic motivators can drive individuals to meet these external standards, maintain discipline, and achieve tangible rewards that are often necessary for professional advancement. While some scholars argue that

extrinsic rewards can undermine intrinsic motivation, especially when used inappropriately, others suggest that a balanced approach that incorporates both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators can be highly effective, particularly in the context of professional training and development.

This study focuses on the motivational orientations of prospective teachers enrolled in the Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) program at Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. The B.Ed. program is designed to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and professional attitudes necessary for a successful career in teaching. However, as these students transition from learners to educators, understanding what drives them—whether it be an intrinsic love for teaching and learning, or extrinsic factors such as grades, career prospects, and societal expectations—is crucial for shaping effective teacher training programs.

The educational landscape in Pakistan, like in many other countries, faces significant challenges. These include the need for well-trained and motivated teachers who can inspire students and raise the overall standards of education. In this context, the motivations of prospective teachers become even more critical. The extent to which these individuals are motivated intrinsically or extrinsically can impact not only their own educational experiences but also the quality of education they will eventually provide to their students.

Previous research has extensively explored the concepts of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, often highlighting their complex interplay. While intrinsic motivation is generally linked to positive educational outcomes, extrinsic motivation has been found to be effective in certain contexts, particularly where external goals and rewards are clearly defined and aligned with the individual's personal aspirations. The debate over the relative importance of these two types of motivation continues, with some studies suggesting that extrinsic rewards can undermine intrinsic motivation, while others propose that the two can coexist and even enhance each other.

The objectives of this research are twofold. First, the study aims to quantitatively assess the levels of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation among students in the B.Ed. program at Bahauddin Zakariya University. Second, it seeks to analyze the implications of these motivational orientations for their future careers as educators. By providing a detailed analysis of the motivational profiles of prospective teachers, this study hopes to inform the design and implementation of more effective teacher education programs. These programs should ideally foster both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, ensuring that future teachers are not only passionate about their work but also equipped to meet the external demands of the profession.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to the ongoing discourse on motivation in education. By focusing on a specific group—prospective teachers in Pakistan—it adds to the understanding of how motivation operates in different cultural and educational contexts. Furthermore, the findings of this study could have practical implications for teacher education programs, helping educators and policymakers develop strategies that support and enhance the motivation of future teachers.

In conclusion, this research addresses a critical aspect of teacher education by exploring the intrinsic and extrinsic motivations of prospective teachers. The findings will not only enrich the academic literature on motivation but also provide actionable insights for improving the effectiveness of teacher training programs. By fostering a balanced approach to motivation, educators can better prepare future teachers to meet the challenges of the profession, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes for students.

Methods

Research Design

This study employs a descriptive research design, which is well-suited for investigating the levels and types of motivation among prospective teachers. Descriptive research allows for a systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of data to describe the current status of a phenomenon. In this case, the study focuses on assessing the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation levels of students enrolled in the Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) program at Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. This design is particularly appropriate for understanding the motivational orientations of a specific group of individuals and identifying patterns and trends within the data.

Participants

The population for this study consisted of 118 students enrolled in the B.Ed. (Hons.) Elementary program at the Department of Education, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan. A sample of 91 students was selected using the Raosoft Sample Calculator, ensuring a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. However, 74 students responded to the survey, resulting in an effective response rate of 81%. The sample included both male and female students, and the participants were representative of the broader population of prospective teachers in the university.

Instrumentation

Data were collected using a specifically designed Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation Scale. The scale consisted of 36 items, equally divided between intrinsic motivation (18 items) and extrinsic motivation (18 items). The items were structured on a 5-point Likert scale, with response options ranging from "Strongly Agree" (5) to "Strongly Disagree" (1). The scale was adapted from existing validated instruments in the literature and was further refined to suit the specific context of the study. The scale was administered online via Google Forms, making it accessible to all participants.

Procedure

The data collection process was conducted over a two-week period. Participants were informed about the study's objectives and assured of the confidentiality of their responses. After obtaining informed consent, the survey link was distributed to the selected students through their university email addresses. Participants were given one week to complete the survey, with reminders sent out midway through the response period to encourage participation.

Data Analysis

The collected data were subjected to rigorous analysis using descriptive statistical methods. The primary statistical techniques employed included the calculation of mean scores, frequency distributions, and percentage analyses for each item on the Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation Scale. The mean scores were used to determine the overall levels of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation among the participants. A mean score greater than 3.00 was interpreted as an indication of positive motivation towards the respective item.

The data were further analyzed to compare the mean scores of intrinsic versus extrinsic motivation, providing insights into the dominant motivational orientation among the prospective teachers. The analysis also involved identifying any significant differences in motivational levels based on demographic variables such as gender and academic performance, although these were not the primary focus of the study.

Reliability and Validity

To ensure the reliability and validity of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted with a small sample of students who were not included in the final analysis. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was calculated to assess the internal consistency of the scale, yielding a value of 0.845 for the 36 items, indicating high reliability. Content validity was established through expert review, wherein the scale items were evaluated by experienced educators and researchers in the field of educational psychology. Feedback from the pilot study was incorporated to refine the scale, ensuring that it accurately measured the intended constructs of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. Approval was obtained from the university's ethics committee prior to data collection. Participants were informed about the voluntary nature of their participation, the purpose of the study, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality of the participants' responses was maintained throughout the study, and data were anonymized prior to analysis to protect the privacy of the individuals involved.

Results

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of all variables

Individual factors	Category	Frequency (%)	Mean	SD
Gender	Male	72 (48.0)	---	---
	Female	78 (52.0)	---	---
Program	Undergraduate	68 (45.3)	---	---
	Postgraduate	82 (54.7)	---	---
Year of Study	1 st	35 (25.0)	---	---
	2 nd	30 (21.4)	---	---
	3 rd	42 (30.0)	---	---
	4 th	33 (23.6)	---	---
Residency	Hostiles	47 (31.3)	---	---
	Day Scholars	81 (54.0)	---	---
CGPA	Up to 2.50	32 (22.9)	---	---
	2.51-3.00	44 (31.4)	---	---

	3.01-3.50	36 (25.7)	---	---
	3.51-4.00	28 (20.0)		
Intrinsic Motivation	---	---	3.89	0.94
Extrinsic Motivation	---	---	3.93	0.93

As shown in table1, shows frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation of study variables.

Table 2: Mean value of student responses for Intrinsic Motivation

Sr. No.	Statement	Mean	SD
1	I like hard work because it's a challenge.	4.32	0.85
2	I would rather try and figure it out by myself.	4.05	0.88
3	I work on problems to learn how to solve them.	4.28	0.95
4	I sometimes think my own ideas are better.	3.87	1.11
5	I know when I have made mistake without checking with the teacher.	3.85	0.98
6	I like difficult problem because they enjoying trying to figure me out.	4.02	1.08
7	I do my class work because the teacher tells too.	4.14	0.82
8	When I make a mistake would rather figure out the right answer by myself.	3.79	1.20
9	I know whether or not I am doing well in without grades.	3.36	0.81
10	I don't agree with the teacher sometime and stick to my own opinion.	4.08	0.88
11	I like to learn thing on own that interest me.	3.74	0.93
12	I read things because I am interest in the subject.	3.87	0.99
13	I keep trying to figure out the problems on my own.	3.90	0.80
14	I like to go on to own work at a more difficult level.	3.45	1.07
15	For me what I think of my work is the most important think.	3.86	0.71
16	I ask question in class because I want to learn new things.	3.86	0.83
17	I pretty much know how well I did even before I get my paper back.	3.75	0.91
18	I like to make my own plan for what to do next.	3.88	1.03

Table 3: Mean value of student responses for Extrinsic Motivation

Sr. No.	Statement	Mean	SD
1	I prefer easy work that I am sure I can do	4.28	0.79
2	When some students don't understand something right away they want the teacher to tell them the answer	3.85	0.92
3	I work on problems because I am supposed too	4.13	0.86
4	I almost always think that what the teacher says to ok	4.08	0.98
5	I need to check with the teacher to know If I have made a mistake.	4.17	1.02
6	I don't like to figure out difficult problems	3.00	1.11
7	I do my class work to find out about a lot of thing I have being wanted to know.	3.89	0.90
8	I would rather ask to teacher how to get the right answer.	3.66	1.08
9	I need to have the grades to know how well I am doing in.	3.90	0.96
10	I agree with the teacher because I think that I teacher is right about most things.	4.10	0.82
11	I think it's better to do things that the teacher I should be learning.	4.08	0.88
12	I read things because the teacher wants me too.	3.9	0.81
13	If I get stuck on a problem I ask the teacher for help.	3.83	0.96
14	I would rather stick to the assignments which are pretty easy to do.	3.72	0.84
15	I think that what the teacher thinks of my work is the most important thinks.	3.80	0.99
16	I ask question because I want the teacher to notice me.	4.03	0.87
17	I am not really sure if I have done well on a test until they get my papers back with the mark on it.	3.88	1.10
18	I like the teacher to help me to plan what to do next.	4.51	0.93

Table 4: Correlation between intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation among students

Variables	Mean ± SD	1	2
Intrinsic Motivation	3.89±0.94	1	
Extrinsic Motivation	3.93±0.93	-.581**	1

Table 4 indicates the correlations between intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation among students. The findings reveal that there is significantly and negative correlated intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation are significantly and negatively correlated with each other.

Summary of Findings

The key findings from this study can be summarized as follows:

1. Intrinsic motivation is slightly more prevalent among prospective teachers than extrinsic motivation, with mean scores of 4.08 and 4.00, respectively.
2. The highest levels of intrinsic motivation were associated with challenges and problem-solving, while the highest levels of extrinsic motivation were linked to the preference for easy tasks.
3. Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are significant drivers for prospective teachers, suggesting the need for a balanced approach in teacher education.
4. No significant gender differences were observed in motivational orientations, indicating consistency across male and female participants.

These results provide valuable insights into the motivational profiles of prospective teachers at Bahauddin Zakariya University and highlight the importance of addressing both intrinsic and extrinsic factors in teacher training programs.

Discussion

This study set out to explore the dynamics of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation among prospective teachers enrolled in the B.Ed. program at Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. The findings provide valuable insights into how these motivational orientations shape the future educators' attitudes towards teaching and learning. A key result was the slight predominance of extrinsic motivation (mean score = 3.93) over intrinsic motivation (mean score = 3.89), which, although marginal, indicates a critical trend in how external incentives are more likely to influence the participants.

The negative correlation observed between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation (-0.581) highlights a complex interplay between the two. This suggests that an increase in dependence on extrinsic factors, such as grades and external validation, could diminish the strength of intrinsic motivation, which is rooted in intellectual curiosity and personal satisfaction. This finding aligns with self-determination theory, which posits that extrinsic motivators, when overemphasized, can undermine intrinsic motivation, leading to a reliance on external validation over personal fulfillment (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

The predominance of extrinsic motivation observed in this study may reflect broader systemic and cultural influences within the educational context of Pakistan. In many educational settings, emphasis on grades, teacher approval, and job prospects often outweighs internal goals of mastery and personal growth. The participants' high mean scores for items such as "I prefer easy work that I am sure I can do" (Mean = 4.28) underscore the importance of task security and external achievement in their motivation. This highlights the need for teacher education programs to address and balance these external pressures with strategies that foster long-term engagement, passion for teaching, and intellectual curiosity.

Implications for Teacher Education

The results suggest that teacher education programs must carefully balance the fostering of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to prepare future educators effectively. While intrinsic motivation is critical for fostering lifelong passion and commitment to the teaching profession, extrinsic motivation remains a necessary driver in ensuring discipline, performance, and meeting external benchmarks such as certifications and job placements. Educational strategies that support both types of motivation could potentially enhance the efficacy of training programs by catering to the dual needs of personal satisfaction and societal expectations.

This study's findings underscore the importance of integrating pedagogical approaches that not only challenge students intellectually but also provide them with clear pathways for external recognition and reward. Collaborative learning, problem-based tasks, and opportunities for independent research can enhance intrinsic motivation, while clear career guidance, performance feedback, and structured achievement goals can address the extrinsic needs of students. These strategies can create a well-rounded educational experience that prepares future teachers for both the personal and professional demands of the teaching career.

Challenges and Areas for Further Research

Despite the valuable insights, this study also reveals areas where further research is needed. The slight dominance of extrinsic motivation, though significant, calls for a more in-depth examination of how intrinsic motivation can be nurtured within the educational context of Pakistan, where external pressures are high.

Future studies should explore longitudinal effects of motivational orientations on career satisfaction, teaching performance, and job retention among educators. Additionally, qualitative research into the personal experiences of prospective teachers could provide deeper insights into how intrinsic and extrinsic motivations evolve throughout their academic and professional journeys.

Another area for exploration is the cultural dimension of motivation in education. The findings raise important questions about how intrinsic and extrinsic motivations vary across different educational environments, particularly in diverse urban, rural, and institutional settings. A comparative analysis of motivational orientations between institutions in different regions of Pakistan or even internationally could enrich our understanding of how educational culture impacts teacher motivation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the slight predominance of extrinsic motivation among the prospective teachers in this study suggests that external factors such as grades, career prospects, and societal expectations hold significant sway over their motivational orientations. However, the continued presence of strong intrinsic motivation, particularly in areas related to problem-solving and intellectual challenges, indicates that future educators still value personal growth and satisfaction. Teacher education programs must leverage this balance by developing curricula that promote both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators, ensuring that educators are not only driven by external success but are also passionate and intellectually engaged in their profession. This balanced approach is essential for producing motivated, committed, and effective educators who can positively impact future generations of learners.

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APPENDIX-A

Intrinsic and Extrinsic motivation scale

An Investigation of prospective teachers’ intrinsic and extrinsic motivation

Gender _____ Program _____
 Semester _____ Day scholar/hostelide _____
 CGPA _____

Each option has a score as explained below you should tick the option keeping in view the score allocated to that particular option.

- Strongly agree (SA)
- Agree (A)
- Undecided (U)
- Disagree (D)
- Strong disagree (SD)

I am not sure if my work is really good or not until the teachers tell me.

SA	A	U	D	SD
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Sr. No.	Statement	5	4	3	2	1
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1	I	<u>I like hard work because it's a challenge</u>	<u>SA</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>U</u>	<u>D</u>	<u>SD</u>
	E	I prefer easy work that I am sure I can do	SA	A	U	D	SD
2	E	<u>When some students don't understand some thing right away they want the teacher to tell them the answer</u>	<u>SA</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>U</u>	<u>D</u>	<u>SD</u>
	I	I would rather try and figure it out by my self	SA	A	U	D	SD
3	I	<u>I work on problems to learn how to solve them.</u>	<u>SA</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>U</u>	<u>D</u>	<u>SD</u>
	E	I work on problems because I am supposed too	SA	A	U	D	SD
4	E	<u>I almost always think that what the teacher say to ok</u>	<u>SA</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>U</u>	<u>D</u>	<u>SD</u>
	I	I sometimes think my own ideas are better	SA	A	U	D	SD
5	I	<u>I know when I have made mistake without checking with the teacher</u>	<u>SA</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>U</u>	<u>D</u>	<u>SD</u>
	E	I need to check with the teacher to know If I have made a mistake.	SA	A	U	D	SD
6	I	<u>I like difficult problem because they enjoying trying to figure me out,</u>	<u>SA</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>U</u>	<u>D</u>	<u>SD</u>
	E	I don't like to figure out difficult problems	SA	A	U	D	SD
7	I	<u>I do my class work because the teacher tells too.</u>	<u>SA</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>U</u>	<u>D</u>	<u>SD</u>
	E	I do my class work to find out about a lot of thing I have being wanted to know.	SA	A	U	D	SD
8	I	<u>When I make a mistake would rather figure out the right answer by my self</u>	<u>SA</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>U</u>	<u>D</u>	<u>SD</u>

	E	I would rather ask to teacher how to get the right answer.	SA	A	U	D	SD
9	I	I know whether or not I am doing well In without grades.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	E	I need to have the grades to know how well I am doing in.	SA	A	U	D	SD
10	E	I agree with the teacher because I think that I teacher is right about most things.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	I	I don't agree with the teacher sometime and stick to my own opinion.	SA	A	U	D	SD
11	I	I like to learn thing on own that interest me.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	E	I think it's better to do things that the teacher I should be learning.	SA	A	U	D	SD
12	I	I read things because I am interest in the subject.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	E	I read things because the teacher wants me too.	SA	A	U	D	SD
13	E	If I get stuck on a problem I ask the teacher for help.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	I	I keep trying to figure out the problems on my own.	SA	A	U	D	SD
14	I	I like to go on to own work at a more difficult level.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	E	I would rather stick to the assignments which are pretty easy to do.	SA	A	U	D	SD
15	E	I think that what the teacher thinks of my work is the most important thinks.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	I	For me what I think of my work is the most important think.	SA	A	U	D	SD

16	I	I ask question in class because I want to learn new things	SA	A	U	D	SD
	E	I ask question because I want the teacher to notice me.	SA	A	U	D	SD
17	E	I am not really sure if I have done well on a test until they get my papers back with the mark on it.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	I	I pretty much know how well I did even before I get my paper back.	SA	A	U	D	SD
18	E	I like the teacher to help me to plan what to do next.	SA	A	U	D	SD
	I	I like to make my own plan for what to do next.	SA	A	U	D	SD